

Data Management Plan for the project “Natural Crosslinker-Infused Bacterial Cellulose Composites with Nanocarbon Networks for High-Performance EMI Shielding”

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) describes the management of research data generated within the postdoctoral research project focused on the development of biodegradable bacterial cellulose (BC) composites reinforced with nanocarbon conductive networks for electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding applications.

The project includes formulation and characterization of bio-based resin systems, processing of BC composites, incorporation of carbon nanotubes (CNTs), EMI shielding characterization, thermal and mechanical testing, durability assessment, and dissemination of results. Generated data will include material formulation datasets, FTIR spectra, rheological measurements, thermal analysis data (TGA/DSC), microscopy images (SEM/AFM), conductivity measurements, EMI shielding data, mechanical testing datasets, and accelerated aging results.

The project follows FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Open Science practices. Research outputs, including datasets and publications, will be deposited in open-access repositories such as Zenodo and institutional repositories where

appropriate. Sensitive or commercially valuable information related to intellectual property will be protected prior to public dissemination.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

PostDoc Latvia

Researchers

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Organizations

Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Data Management Plan for the project "Natural Crosslinker-Infused Bacterial Cellulose Composites with Nanocarbon Networks for High-Performance EMI Shielding"](#)

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Researchers:

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: [Latvian Council of Science](#) | [LCS](#)

Grants: [PostDoc Latvia](#)

Project: [Natural Crosslinker-Infused Bacterial Cellulose Composites with Nanocarbon Networks for High-Performance EMI Shielding](#)

3. License

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4. Templates

Descriptions

[Research Data Management for Biodegradable Bacterial Cellulose EMI Shielding Composites](#)

This description outlines the data management procedures for the postdoctoral research project focused on the development of biodegradable bacterial cellulose (BC) composites reinforced with nanocarbon conductive networks for electromagnetic interference (EMI) shielding applications. The generated research data include composite formulation records, FTIR spectra, rheological measurements, microscopy images, conductivity measurements, EMI shielding characterization, mechanical testing results, thermal analysis data, and durability testing datasets. The description follows FAIR data principles and Open Science practices to ensure long-term accessibility, interoperability, reproducibility, and reusability of research outputs.

Template: [Science Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Description And Collection Or Re-use Of Existing Data

1.2 Data Description And Collection Or Re-use Of Existing Data

1.2.2 How will new data be collected or produced and/or how will existing data be re-used?

1.2.2.2 Explain which methodologies or software will be used if new data are collected or produced

The project will generate experimental data through laboratory synthesis, processing, and characterization of biodegradable bacterial cellulose (BC) composites reinforced with conductive nanocarbon fillers. Methodologies include vacuum-assisted impregnation, thermal curing, rheological characterization, FTIR spectroscopy, thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), scanning electron microscopy (SEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), electrical conductivity measurements, EMI shielding measurements, and accelerated ageing tests. Data analysis and visualization will be performed using scientific software such as OriginPro and instrument-specific analysis software.

OriginPro

1.2.2.3 Are there any constraints on the re-use of existing data?

No

Comment:

The project primarily generates original experimental datasets. Literature and publicly available reference datasets may be consulted for benchmarking and comparison purposes only.

1.2.2.4 Explain how data provenance will be documented

Primary data

Data provenance will be tracked through structured laboratory notebooks, electronic records, metadata files, sample identifiers, instrument logs, and version-controlled processed datasets. Each dataset will contain information about sample composition, preparation conditions, processing parameters, measurement dates, and responsible researchers.

1.2.2.5 Briefly state the reasons if the re-use of any existing data sources has been considered but discarded

Existing datasets available in literature are insufficient for the objectives of this project because the proposed bacterial cellulose-based EMI shielding composites use novel combinations of bio-based crosslinkers, conductive nanocarbon networks, and processing approaches. Therefore, new experimental datasets must be generated.

1.2.3 What data (for example the kind, formats, and volumes), will be collected or produced?

1.2.3.2 Give details on the data types

- numeric (databases, spreadsheets)
- image

Comment:

The project will generate primarily experimental and observational scientific data. These include:

raw instrument output files,

processed analytical datasets,

microscopy images,

conductivity maps,

mechanical testing datasets,

thermal analysis data,

EMI shielding measurements,

formulation and processing records,

statistical analysis files.

Both primary raw data and processed secondary analytical data will be generated during the project.

1.2.3.3 Give details on the data format

- Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language)
- Text files - MS Word docs, .txt files, PDF, RTF, XML (Extensible Markup Language)
- Instrument specific formats - Olympus Confocal Microscope Data Format, Carl Zeiss

Comment:

CSV

TXT

XLSX

PDF

TIFF

PNG

JPEG

instrument-specific spectroscopy and microscopy formats

1.2.3.4 Justify the use of certain formats

No

Comment:

Open and non-proprietary formats such as CSV, TXT, TIFF, and PDF will be

preferred whenever possible to maximize interoperability, long-term accessibility, and reusability. Certain proprietary instrument formats may be temporarily required during data acquisition and analysis because they are generated directly by scientific instrumentation and manufacturer software. Processed exports suitable for long-term preservation will additionally be generated in open formats.

1.2.3.5 Give details on the volumes

GB (gigabyte)

Comment:

2 to 10 GB, the project lifetime, including raw characterization files, microscopy images, processed analytical data, and supplementary documentation.

2 Documentation And Data Quality

2.3 Documentation And Data Quality

2.3.2 What metadata and documentation will accompany the data?

2.3.2.2 Indicate which metadata will be provided to help others identify and discover the data

Yes

Comment:

dataset title,

creator(s),

institutional affiliation,

project identifier,

2.3.2.3 Indicate which metadata standards will be used

Data Package

Comment:

The project will primarily use the Data Package metadata approach together with repository-supported descriptive metadata to ensure FAIR compliance, interoperability, and long-term reusability. Metadata will include dataset title,

authors, affiliations, keywords, methodology descriptions, sample composition, processing parameters, measurement conditions, units, file formats, and licensing information. Additional repository-specific metadata provided by Zenodo and institutional repositories will also be used.

2.3.2.4 Indicate how the data will be organised during the project

Files and folders will follow structured naming conventions including project acronym, work package, sample identifier, analysis method, and date.

BC_CNT_WP3_SEM_2027_05_01.tiff

Version numbers will be applied to processed datasets and analysis files. Repository-based versioning systems and dated file revisions will be used to track updates and modifications.

2.3.2.5 Consider what other documentation is needed to enable re-use

Additional documentation will include: experimental protocols, sample preparation methods, processing parameters, instrument settings, data analysis procedures, README files, variable definitions, units of measurement, calibration information.

2.3.2.6 Consider how this information will be captured and where it will be recorded

- 'readme' text file
- lab notebooks
- other

Comment:

Recommended selection:

README files

laboratory notebooks

repository data

electronic documentation

2.3.3 What data quality control measures will be used?

2.3.3.1 Explain how the consistency and quality of data collection will be controlled and documented

- calibration
- repeated samples or measurements
- standardised data capture

3 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.4 Storage And Backup During The Research Process

3.4.2 How will data and metadata be stored and backed up during the research?

3.4.2.2 Describe where the data will be stored and backed up during research activities and how often the backup will be performed

Comment:

Research data will be stored on secure RTU institutional servers and password-protected institutional computers. Backup copies will be maintained automatically and synchronized regularly using institutional IT infrastructure. Important datasets will additionally be archived on external secure storage systems and trusted repositories.

3.4.3 How will data security and protection of sensitive data be taken care of during the research?

3.4.3.2 Explain how the data will be recovered in the event of an incident

In the event of accidental deletion, hardware failure, or cyber incident, data will be recovered from institutional backup systems and synchronized storage copies maintained by RTU IT infrastructure.

3.4.3.3 Explain who will have access to the data during the research and how access to data is controlled, especially in collaborative partnerships

- Identification
- Authentication

- Authorization

Comment:

Access to unpublished research data will be limited to authorized project researchers, supervisors, and collaborating institutional partners involved in the project activities.

3.4.3.4 Describe the main risks and how these will be managed

other

Main risks accidental deletion, hardware failure, data corruption, unauthorized access, loss of unpublished results, temporary equipment failure.

Comment:

Risks will be mitigated through regular backups, secure institutional infrastructure, password-protected systems, version control, duplicate storage locations, and repository archiving of finalized datasets.

3.4.3.5 Explain which institutional data protection policies are in place

RTU institutional IT security and data protection policies will be followed during the project.

4 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.5 Legal And Ethical Requirements, Codes Of Conduct

4.5.2 Personal data

4.5.2.2 If personal data are processed, how will compliance with legislation on personal data and on security be ensured?

The project does not involve human participants or collection of personal data. Therefore, GDPR-sensitive personal information is not expected to be processed within the generated research datasets.

4.5.2.3 Explain whether there is a managed access procedure in place for authorised users of personal data

No managed access procedure for personal data is required because no personal or sensitive human data will be collected.

4.5.2 How will other legal issues, such as intellectual property rights and ownership, be managed? What legislation is applicable?

4.5.2.2 Data ownership and accessibility

4.5.2.2.2 Who will be the owner of the data

Oskars Platnieks (orcid: [0000-0001-5529-0912](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-5529-0912))

4.5.2.2.3 Explain what access conditions will apply to the data?

- ethical
- commercial sensitivity

4.5.2.2.4 Will the data be openly accessible, or will there be access restrictions?

Openly accessible

4.5.2.3 Intellectual property rights

4.5.2.3.2 Are intellectual property rights affected?

No

4.5.2.4 Third-party data restrictions

4.5.2.4.2 Indicate whether there are any restrictions on the re-use of third-party data.

There are no significant restrictions anticipated regarding third-party datasets because the project primarily generates original experimental data.

4.5.4 Ethical issues

4.5.4.2 What ethical issues and codes of conduct (CoC) are there, and how will they be taken into account?

The project does not involve human participants, clinical data, or sensitive personal information. Potential intellectual property considerations related to novel materials and formulations may affect temporary access restrictions before publication.

Other

Comment:

Secure institutional storage systems, controlled researcher access, and repository-based publication procedures will be used to protect unpublished datasets and commercially relevant information.

5 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.6 Data Sharing And Long-term Preservation

5.6.2 How and when will data be shared? Are there possible restrictions to data sharing or embargo reasons?

5.6.2.2 Explain how the data will be discoverable and shared

deposit in a data repository

Comment:

Datasets will be deposited in trusted repositories with metadata, keywords, DOI identifiers, and links to associated scientific publications.

Datasets will be shared through repositories such as Zenodo and institutional repositories following FAIR and Open Science principles.

5.6.2.3 Outline the plan for data preservation and give information on how long the data will be retained

Published datasets and associated metadata will be retained for at least 10 years after publication.

2026-10-01

5.6.2.4 Explain when the data will be made available

upon publication

5.6.2.5 Indicate the expected timely release

2027-06-30

5.6.2.6 Will exclusive use of the data be claimed?

No

5.6.2.8 Indicate whether data sharing will be postponed or restricted

Postponed

Temporary embargo periods may be required until scientific publication or intellectual property assessment is completed.

5.6.2.9 Indicate who will be able to use the data

Researchers, students, industry partners, governmental organizations, and the broader scientific community may use openly published datasets.

5.6.2.10 Is it necessary to restrict access to certain communities or to apply a data sharing agreement?

No

5.6.3 How will data for preservation be selected, and where data will be preserved long-term?

5.6.3.2 Indicate what data must be retained or destroyed for contractual, legal, or regulatory purposes.

Retained

5.6.3.3 Indicate how it will be decided what data to keep

Datasets associated with scientific publications, reproducibility of results, long-term scientific value, and FAIR/Open Science requirements will be preserved long-term.

5.6.3.4 Describe the data to be preserved long-term

processed analytical datasets, microscopy images, thermal analysis data, conductivity and EMI shielding measurements, metadata, protocols, README documentation, published supplementary materials.

5.6.3.5 Explain the foreseeable research uses (and/ or users) for the data.

The datasets may support future research in: biodegradable composites, EMI shielding materials, sustainable polymers, nanocomposites, thermal management materials, circular bioeconomy technologies.

5.6.3.6 Indicate where the data will be deposited

Zenodo; RTU institutional repository

5.6.3.7 Will there be established repository proposed?

Yes

5.6.3.8 Demonstrate that the data can be curated effectively beyond the lifetime of the grant

Trusted repositories such as Zenodo provide DOI assignment, metadata support, versioning, long-term preservation infrastructure, and FAIR-compliant access mechanisms.

5.6.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access and use data?

5.6.4.1 Indicate how the data will be shared

Data will be shared through trusted repositories, supplementary publication materials, and institutional Open Science platforms.

5.6.4.2 Indicate whether potential users need specific tools to access and (re-)use the data

Possible services: Excel, LibreOffice, Python, ImageJ, OriginPro

Comment:

Most processed datasets will be accessible using commonly available scientific and office software tools.

5.6.5 How will the application of a unique and persistent identifier to each data set be ensured?

5.6.5.2 Explain how the data might be re-used in other contexts

The datasets may support comparative studies, development of sustainable conductive materials, machine learning analysis of material performance, and future composite engineering research.

5.6.5.3 Indicate whether a persistent identifier for the data will be pursued

Yes

Digital Object Identifier (DOI)

Comment:

DOI identifiers assigned by trusted repositories will ensure persistent discoverability and citation of datasets.

6 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.7 Data Management Responsibilities And Resources

6.7.2 Who will be responsible for data management?

6.7.2.2 Outline the roles and responsibilities for data management/stewardship activities

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Data management Data stewardship Metadata preparation Repository deposition DMP maintenance

6.7.2.3 Is it a collaborative project?

No

6.7.3 What resources will be dedicated to data management and ensuring that data will be FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Re-usable)?

6.7.3.2 Explain how the necessary resources (for example time) to prepare the data for sharing/preservation (data curation) have been costed in

The project budget and institutional infrastructure will support: secure storage, backup systems, repository deposition, metadata preparation, documentation, FAIR/Open Science compliance activities.

6.7.3.3 Indicate whether additional resources will be needed to prepare data for deposit or to meet any charges from data repositories

No

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